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ORGANIZATIONAL DIAGNOSIS THROUGH AN ESTIMATION OF THE PRODUCTION FUNCTION CASE STUDY OF A NIGERIAN BREWERY [1991-2000]

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Abstract

Indian experience shows that human resource managers seldom undertake an analysis of the organization to ascertain its health of an organization before implementing any strategic intervention. At best they look at an analysis of financial ratios and that in this author's opinion is not enough. It is opined that before any strategic policy intervention takes place it is imperative that management diagnoses the economic health of the organization. Using data from a Nigerian brewery owned by a multinational enterprise (Unilever) this paper has attempted to demonstrate how the economic health of an organization can be gauged. The data is old no doubt but the point being made here is to demonstrate "how" to undertake an organizational diagnosis using mainstream economics and nothing else.

Key Words: Cobb-Douglas Organizational Diagnosis Estimating Production Function

1. Introduction: *In economics, the term production function relates physical output of a production process to physical inputs or factors of production. The production function is one of the key concepts of mainstream neoclassical theories, used to define marginal product and to distinguish allocative efficiency, the defining focus of economics. The primary purpose of the production function is to address allocative efficiency in the use of factor inputs in production and the resulting distribution of income to those factors, while abstracting away from the technological problems of achieving technical efficiency, as an engineer or professional people manager might understand it. The Cobb–Douglas production function is a particular functional form of the production function that is widely used to represent the technological relationship between the amounts of two or more inputs, particularly physical capital and labor, and the amount of*

output that can be produced by those inputs. The Cobb-Douglas form was developed and tested against statistical evidence by Charles Cobb and Paul Douglas during 1927–1947. The estimation and use of production function has become a widespread and important practice in economic analysis. Inferences derived from empirical studies have shown the importance of the rate of returns on investment, share of wages in, vis-à-vis labour's contributions to production and the technical and economic forces making for firm's growth. It follows therefore, that an attempt to view the economic performance of a firm must be viewed in the light of its output-capital-labour relationship (i.e. its production function). The significance of this exercise (i.e. estimating the production function of the beer industry) can be fully appreciated when the firm is faced with a situation of having to choose among several policy options concerning the right combination of factor inputs to achieve a given level of output that maximizes profit. Be this as it may, the exercise has academic as well as practical uses. It gauges the economic health (well-being) of the company.

In macroeconomics, aggregate production functions are estimated to create a framework in which to distinguish how much of economic growth to attribute to changes in factor allocation (e.g. the accumulation of capital) and how much to attribute to advancing technology. Some non-mainstream economists, however, reject the very concept of an aggregate production function. This paper understandably attempts a micro economic analysis since the author takes a position to the effect that Piero Sraffa had successfully read the last rites of the macro production function decades ago! So too the paper sustains its logic and method on the basic Cobb Douglas formulation rather than the more advanced CES formulation. This case study must therefore be seen as an attempt to examine the conceptualization of the relationship between a firm's inputs and its output technically known as the production function. It is this framework that not only provides the need form but also shapes the pattern of a firm's policy, and therefore from the basis of an individual firm's behavioural /operational calculus.

Production functions are furthermore said to be invariant to economic and some behavioural factors especially market and industry condition because it seeks to answer the following question:

- 1. Returns to scale i.e. whether a firm enjoys increasing or diminishing returns to scale;*
- 2. Allocation efficiency i.e., whether a firm purchase and utilize factor inputs in the most efficient manner and to make inter firm comparisons in resource allocation;*
- 3. Returns to factor inputs. The production function tells us the desirability of either subsidizing or taxing the use of a particular input if returns to the factor input are increasing or diminishing in a certain range. It also makes it possible for policy makers especially government to encourage the use of certain domestic factor inputs if such factor experiences increasing returns to scale. This becomes very crucial when the government adopts an import-substitution industrialization strategy.*
- 4. The production function tells us the degree of substitutability between inputs as measured by the elasticity of substitution This is very crucial to the distribution to total output between different inputs and the examination of the effects of exogenous changes in factor prices (e.g. minimum wage legislation and changes in the quantities of labour supplied due to the relaxation of migration policy) on returns to factors and their share in total output of the firm.*
- 5. The production function also provides solution to such problems and the distribution of National income between income classes and it provide empirical explanations to inter-country and inter-temporal differences in economic growth of GNP.*

The answering of these questions depends on our ability to correctly identify the production function i.e. isolating the purely technological relationships from the economic, behavioural and other historical relationships that bears on production activity. If we can do this, then we will be right in our claim that our explanation of the relative efficiency of firms with respect to parameters such as prices structure of industry, size and past experiences of firms. We need, to emphasize here that the estimation of the production function from observed data is done such that the invariance conditions are preserved.

2. The Basics: Production can simply be viewed as the creation of value whereas consumption is the destruction of that value. Value creation is seen in terms of output of goods, commodities and services that satisfy the utility function of consumers. The four classical factors of production are Land, Labour, Capital and Management. Land is finite and Management is an agent of capital so we can discount them. Labour is the human effort put into producing goods, commodities and services. Capital is human-made aid to production and investment signifies the process of capital creation.

Let Q stand for Value of Output {gleaned from the Chair persons's Annual Report}

Let L stand for Labour {taken from the Wage Bill in the company balance sheet}

Let K stand for Capital. {taken from Net Bloc given in the company balance sheet}

All these values are in given annually in currency dominations. And all of them are taken from public documents created by the firm or corporation over at least a decade.

Let α stand for ΔQ due to an infinitesimal change in Labour Input L when Capital K is held constant.

Let β stand for ΔQ due to an infinitesimal change in Capital Input K when Labour L is held constant.

One gets the value of α and β through differentiating L and K against Q respectively.

Let A signify the level of technology.

A , α and β are then output elasticities determined by the data.

The elementary production function is then stated as $Q = A L^\alpha K^\beta$

We have data for all Q , K , L , α and β either taken from or calculated from public documents. But what about A we would then ask?

We must convert a simple linear equation above into a log linear equation thus:

$\log Q = \log A + \alpha \log L + \beta \log K$. We then solve for A

If $A \leq 3$ then PTG (pray to God). Since A is nothing but the proxy for the Investment Multiplier its value does matter a lot in determining the "health" of the organization under study. In short, technology must be such that Rs 1 invested is converted to Rs 3 output at the very least for the production unit to remain viable.

The condition of Cobb-Douglas function that under equilibrium $\alpha + \beta = 1$ is retained. Hence we can state

If $\alpha + \beta > 1$ the firm operates under conditions of increasing returns to scale

If $\alpha + \beta = 1$ the firm operates under conditions of constant returns to scale

If $\alpha + \beta < 1$ the firm operates under conditions of decreasing returns to scale

This result is then treaded off against the value of A to judge the economic health of the production unit or firm or corporation.

3. Advanced Treatment: The pioneering econometric estimation of a production function by Douglas was undertaken to explain the distribution of revenue between wages and profit. Their starting point was the observed revenue shares of wages and profits in total revenue leading to a search for a production function in terms of output and inputs which could explain these observed shares. The simple Cobb-Douglas production function is used in this paper for Guinness (Nig.) Ltd between 1991 and 2000. Guinness (Nig) Ltd is a part of the great Unilever Industrial Empire that has had traditionally deep rooted economic interests in Nigeria.

If the factor inputs change by “t”, output will be:

$$tQ=F(tK,tL)\dots\dots\dots(2)$$

If this is taken as given, then the production function can be written in a compact form where output per head depends on capital i.e.

$$Q=F(K,L)\dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$tQ=f(tK,tL)\dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Assuming that $t=1/L$, then equation 4 becomes:

$$Q/L=f(K/L,1)\dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$Q=f(K)\dots\dots\dots(6)$$

where $Q = Q/L$ and $K=K/L$

We retain the notion that the marginal productivity of labour and capital is positive but diminishes within the domain of the production function. This means that if the labour stock of capital, total output will increase. In other words if we increase labour with a given stock of capital or machines we certainly ceteris paribus would expect to be able to produce more.

We also retain the notion that the firm aims at least cost combination of resources. In other words, it aims at the resource combination which keep its cost outlay for given level of output as low as possible.

5. Hypotheses: Given the assumptions above, we could safely hypothesize as follows:

1. That the economic performance of the firm in terms of productivity (and perhaps price) is a function of the resource inputs combination and efficiency.
2. That capacity utilization is a function of the technical efficiency of factors inputs.
3. That the firm achieves its greatest economic efficiency (lowest cost per unit of product) at the ratio of labour to capital that maximizes product per unit of labour/capital.
4. That productivity measured as value-added is a positive function of labour wages.
5. That labour employment is a negative function of wages and a positive function of its marginal productivity,
6. That the technique of production adopted is a negative function of factor prices.

6. Methodology: Time series technique is used in analyzing the data collected. This is because production is a dynamic item in a firm’s policy package which can only be accurately studied over time. Secondly, we are concerned with the production technique of one firm in the beer industry. We are therefore not taking a cross-sectional look at the beer industry, the time series suffices our purpose. A few words about our data problems and associated aggregation is in order.

1. A consideration of a single observation of values of Q, K and L does not guarantee that the particular value of Q observed is the maximum level of output for the given values of K and L. This is because the firm has a desired usage of K and L that will produce the profit maximizing output.
2. Since we are using time series data, we run into a problem of a changing optimal combination of factors for relative price change over time, This change in relative factor prices affects resource combinations and hence production.

3. *Notwithstanding, our assumptions of labour homogeneity, the quality of administrative and entrepreneurial skills changes positively in the upward direction with longer experience. Therefore there may be movement from sub-optimal utilization of factors. That is, as knowledge increases processes which are technologically more efficient becomes available and the skill and quality of labour strength improves. The result is that rate of productivity of factor inputs, substitutability between factors, efficiency parameters and the economies of scale behaviour of firm will all change. Thus the estimated parameters and at times the mathematical form of the production function change over time this does not however erode our confidence in the assumption made earlier about technical progress which is taken as given. Similarly, our production function is “Hicks neutral” since the marginal rate of substitution of capital for labour is unchanged by technical progress. If old machines are retained for production in spite of new discoveries and technological progress then it is obvious that increase in output is possible only through investment in new machines.*

To re-state our paradigm, in this study Cobb-Douglas production function provides the useful background for the analysis. This type of function takes the general form:

$$Q = boL^{b_1}K^{b_2}U \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

In its original form the sum of the exponents were constrained to equal to unity so that the function becomes:

$$Q = boL^{b_1}K^{1-b_1}u \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where Q is output, L is labour, K is capital and U is a random disturbance term. Although this exponential type of production function has no more claim to general validity as a description than other mathematical functions it has several interesting properties that make it a useful choice for empirical investigations. Some of these features which made us to choose the Cobb-Douglas function are:

1. *There exist problems in aggregating data either by firm of firm to industry. The result of aggregation from the firm to industry level is made simple in the case of the Cobb Douglas by the imposition of identical parameters for all the labour inputs and also the capital inputs. This allows the aggregate functions to be easily estimated provided the data are geometric averages. This is not so for the CES function.*
2. *The Cobb-Douglas function graduates data on output and input better than the CES.*
3. *The function can easily be transformed into a linear function by taking the logarithms of the mathematical expression. This makes it easy and possible to estimate the parameters using OLS multiple regression analysis approach. This is not so with the CES.*

The function has constant elasticities of output variation with respect to labour of capital. Thus the estimated coefficients of the function (i.e. b_1 and b_2) are elasticities of output variation with respect to labour and capital respectively. They indicate the percentage increase or decrease in output associated with a one percent increase or decrease in each of the inputs. In the general and original form of the Cobb-Douglas function the sum of the elasticities equals one (i.e. $b_1 + b_2 = 1$). That is the function is homogenous of degree one thus ensuring constant returns to scale. This can be easily proved as follows: If both inputs are increased by t , then output will increase by t also. From our model, increase in L and K to tL and tK results in and output of:-

$$\begin{aligned} bo(tL)^{b_1} (tK)^{1-b_1} &= t^{b_1 + (1-b_1)} [boL^{b_1}K^{1-b_1}] \\ &= t (b_1 - b_1 + 1) [boL^{b_1}K^{1-b_1}] \\ &= t (boL^{b_1}K^{1-b_1}) \\ &= tQ \dots\dots\dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

We have adapted this function from its original form by replacing the exponent of capital which was $(1-b_1)$ by b_2 . Now if $b_1+b_2>1$ then the firm experiences increasing returns to scale. If $b_1+b_2<1$, then the firm experiences decreasing returns to scale. If $b_1+b_2=1$ then the firm experiences constant returns to scale, given our original assumptions.

By employing the Cobb-Douglas production function, we are making an implicit assumption about the nature of the elasticity of substitution in Guinness (Nig) Ltd., Benin City. The elasticity of substitution as originally set forth by J.R.Hicks provides a measure of the rate of change in the marginal rate of substitution of factors of production in the production of a particular commodity. Technically the elasticity of substitution is:

$$E_s = \frac{\frac{d(k/l)}{(k/l)} \times \frac{(dk/dl)}{d(dk/dl)}}{\dots\dots\dots(4)}$$

In Cobb-Douglas function this is equal to one (i.e. $E_s=1$).

This can however vary from zero to infinity. By using the Cobb-Douglas function in this study, we are assuming that the elasticities of substitution in Guinness are equal to one. If this assumption is found to be incorrect, we will be committing a specification error of unknown magnitude. It will therefore become doubtful whether Cobb-Douglas function is the appropriate model for our data. J.O. Osakwe in the 1980s adopted a simpler method for estimating the elasticity of substitution in Nigerian manufacturing industry which included the Brewery industry in 1976 and found out that the Cobb-Douglas function was adequate. His estimations were based on the observation that output per head was a changing proportion of wage rate. That is:

$$Q/L=C_0 W^{c_1} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

By transforming this into logarithmic form we obtain

$$\log (Q/L) = \log C_0 + C_1 \log W \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

A simple OLS method is then used to estimate C_1 . If C_1 is significantly different from unity, Cobb-Douglas function is inappropriate for the industry or firm and if it is not statistically significantly different from unit, then Cobb-Douglas function provides and adequate fit to the data of the firm.

The required capital and labour coefficients of the Cobb-Douglas production can easily be estimated by means of linear regression. Although the function is non-linear (i.e. $Q= b_0L^{b_1} K^{b_2}$), it can be transformed into a linear function by converting all the variables to logarithms. The function then becomes:

$$\log Q = \log b_0 + b_1 \log L+ b_2 \log K \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

In using the Cobb-Douglas function it is important to test whether the production is homogenous of degree one. That is, to test whether the sum of the labour and capital coefficients is significantly different from one. Put differently it is important to test whether the company is operating under decreasing or increasing returns to scale. This can be carried out by the method suggested by Tintner, (and also quoted elsewhere) as follows:

Let Q_1 be the sum of squares of residuals from the regression equation $Q = b_0L^{b_1} K^{b_2} U$. Let Q_2 be the sum of squares of residuals of the regression under the restriction the sum of the coefficients is unity (i.e. $Q = b_0L^{b_1} K^{1-b_1} U$). It can be shown, according to Tintner, under the null hypothesis that the sum of the regression coefficients equals unity, the $F = (Q_1 - Q_2 / Q_2) \times (N-P)$ follows the F- distribution with one and $(N-P)$ degrees of freedom, where N is the total number of observations and P is the number of variables used. If the F-values calculated in the above manner exceed the F-values at the appropriate significance level, it would indicate that the returns to scale differ significantly from unity. In its original form, the Cobb-Douglas Function was constrained to equal one as $Q = b_0 L^{b_1} K^{1-b_1}U$. For the purpose of this exercise, i.e. testing the homogeneity

condition of the Cobb-Douglas function as far as Guinness Company is concerned; this function can be manipulated to yield the following relationship:

$$Q/L = b_0 (K/L)^{b_1} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

i.e. $\log (Q/L - \log b_0 + b_1 \log (K/L) \dots\dots\dots(9)$

The parameters can then be easily estimated by simple regression method.

7. Estimation Problem: There are likely two statistical problems associated with the use of this single-equation-least squares estimation procedure, one of which is the problem of multi-co linearity. This is a problem that arises from a linear dependence of or correlation between two or more explanatory variables of a model a la Klein. He concluded that the estimates of previous attempts to compute the Cobb-Douglas production function are not plagued by multi co linearity. We therefore stuck to the original Capital and Labour input model. Hasenkamp had later by using two sets of US railroad data with two outputs and three inputs estimated production function parameters through (a) a system of derived input demand functions and (b) the dual cost function. The results indicated increasing returns of scale and a violation of required convexity for the production function. We assume that there no linear dependence and therefore that our estimate does not suffer from this problem.

Another problem that arises from the single equation least squares method of estimation of the production function is that of least squares bias. Technically, least squares bias arises whenever there is two way causation between the independent variables and the dependent variable. In production analysis, the output, labour input and capital input are all endogenous variables which are subject to simultaneous entrepreneurial decisions. Thus, the least squares bias impacted by this multidirectional causation pattern can only be eliminated by a simultaneous equation system-a task which is much more complicated and intricate than the one we have chosen, and therefore lies outside the scope of this study. The single equation-least-squares estimation method is adopted in this study because in our opinion, the explanatory variables are truly exogenous. That is, there is one-way causation between the dependent variable Q and the explanatory variables L and K. Put differently, to avoid the problem of technical or simultaneous equations bias, we assume that output produced is a function of labour and capital inputs; but that labour and capital inputs employed in the production of the output is not a function of the level of output of the company.

The data used in this analysis consisted of a collection of output, labour and capital statistics obtained from published reports of Guinness (Nig.) Ltd., Benin City between 1991 and 2000. Although purely physical measures of the variables would have been preferred, such data were not available in the form required. Value figures in monetary terms are therefore used. Total value of output is used as opposed to value-added overtime. This is because the value-added approach assumes implicitly that raw materials are used in fixed proportion to output. For this reason raw materials are subtracted from the value for output in the use of raw materials. As Klein pointed out, this treatment implies that:

$$(Q-M) = b_0 L^{b_1} K^{b_2} \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

or $Q = M + b_0 L^{b_1} K^{b_2} \dots\dots\dots(11)$

Where M is raw material input measured in monetary terms, to test whether there is significant statistical evidence of economies of scale in the use of raw materials, the following equation could be used.

$$\log Q = b \log M \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

Where Q is total value of output, and M is total value of raw materials. If there are no economies of scale in the use of raw materials, the estimated coefficient b of m would be equal to one.

The Contributions of Labour to Increases in Productivity needs to be examined at this point. With the aid of the production function contributions made by labour to rise in production could be estimated. Thus labour share of increase in production is:

$$\frac{b_1 dL \times dQ}{b_1 dL \times b_2 dK} \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

Where dQ, dL, dK are changes in productivity, employment capital and other inputs respectively and b₁ and b₂ are the elasticities with respect of the labour, and capital inputs respectively. Osakwie had said that changes in productivity, employment and capital could be obtained by fitting a double logarithmic function of the form.

$$\log Q = \log G_1 + t \log b_1 \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

$$\log L = \log G_2 + t \log b_2 \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

$$\log K = \log G_3 + t \log b_3 \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

Where Q, L and K stands for the respective indices of volume of production, employment and capital respectively, b's are the coefficients of production, labour and capital. We however used equation 13 directly without fitting a double-logarithmic function for production, employment and capital.

8. Productivity and Wages of Labour: The estimated production function makes it possible to calculate the marginal productivity of labour. In the case of the Cobb-Douglas production function, the marginal product of labour is:-

$$Q = b_0 L^{b_1} K^{b_2}$$

$$\frac{dQ}{dL} = b_1, b_0 L^{b_1-1} K^{b_2}$$

$$= b_1, b_0 L^{b_1} K^{b_2}$$

$$= \frac{b_1 Q}{L} \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

If labour is paid exactly the value of its marginal product then MPL/W=1. Hence for MPL/W greater than one, it implies that labour is under compensated and for MPL/W less than one, means that labour is over-compensated in relation to its marginal product.

If each unit of labour is paid its marginal product as indicated above, then the payment to labour will be:

$$WL = L \frac{dQ}{dL}$$

$$= b_1 Q \dots\dots\dots(18)$$

Thus labour's share of the total product is b₁ Q similarly, capital's share can be shown to be equal to b₂ Q. Adam Smith in his magnum opus [An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations] had singled out the productivity of labour as the cause of the wealth of nations, seeing in labour's productivity, the principal source of every increase in the productive capacity of any firm. No wonder Karl Marx said that if all values are created by labour, why must all returns not go to labour. For according to Marx, the value of commodity by definition is the quantity of labour that is socially necessary for its production. All these point to the fact that labour should be adequately compensated to ensure higher productivity.

Illustrated here are some aspects of the theory outlined previously by means of data from Guinness (Nig.) Limited. Not all aspects of the theory of production is covered. We are particularly concerned with scale factors elasticity of substitution, marginal productivity of factors and the general estimate of the Cobb-Douglas production function. This perhaps represents the more special features of our approach which are therefore in need of empirical illustrations and verifications. We need to say at the outset that all the production relationships considered are all deterministic and do not allow for random effects. The most crucial step in any applied econometric study like this is the accurate specification of the model. Every econometric equation contains a deterministic part and stochastic part. The deterministic part is specified based on a priori economic theory. So a production function is said to be deterministic if there is no stochastic process.

Re-specification of the Model at this juncture would help Generally the production function could be specified as:

$$Q=f(K,L,U) \dots\dots\dots I$$

Where Q= output, K=capital input, L=labour input and U=disturbance factor. By fitting a Cobb-Douglas function into the general form we obtain:

$$Q= b_0 L^{b_1} K^{b_2} e^u \dots\dots\dots II$$

This, transformed into a logarithmic function gives us:

$$\log Q = \log b_0 + b_1 \log L + b_2 \log K + U \dots\dots\dots III$$

Given that the function has transformed its non-linear conditions to a logarithm linear form, we applied ordinary, least squares (OLS) technique to estimate the parameters which are b_0 , b_1 and b_2 . All the assumptions of the OLS are implicitly accepted as tenable in this study.

9. Empirical Results: The results of production analysis based on the information in table II in appendix reveals the following:

- a) Constant term is - 7.441.
- b) Labour coefficient is 0.745.
- c) Capital coefficient is 0.787.
- d) R^2 i.e. determinant of goodness of fit is 0.963.
- e) R^2 Adjusted R^2 is 0.945.
- f) F-ratio i.e. a measure of the overall significance of the regression analysis is 52.307.

The estimated regression equation is:

$$\log Q = - 7.441 + 0.745 \log L + 0.787 \log K + U \dots\dots\dots IV$$

On the basis of both adjusted coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) and analysis of variance carried out as shown by the F-ratio test, Cobb-Douglas function provided a reasonably good fit to the data for the company. Our estimate of labour and capital coefficient is not significant at 5 and 10 percent level of significance. They are however significant at 20 percent level of significant of significance. The constant term is significant at 5 percent level of significance.

The elasticity of substitution of factor could not be estimated directly using the popular formula of:

$$E_s = \frac{\text{Percentage change in K/L}}{\text{Percentage in MRS}} \dots\dots\dots V$$

Therefore the formula suggested by Tintner which is based on the observation that output per head is a changing proportion of wage rate was used. That is:

$$O/L = C_0 W^{C_1} \dots\dots\dots VI$$

By logarithmic transformation, we obtain:

$$\text{Log } (Q/L) = \text{log } C_0 + C_1 \text{ log } W \dots\dots\dots VII$$

Using simple OLS method, we estimated the parameters are as follows:

$$C_1 = 0.594$$

The significant testing of this reveals that C_1 is not significantly different from unity. It follows that the elasticity of substitution in Guinness (Nig) Limited, Benin City is not significantly different from unity at 5 percent probability level. However a test of the homogeneity conditions reveals that the company operates at increasing returns to scale.

From the estimates of the labour and capital coefficients, it would appear that production would expand more with increase in capital input. This means that the company tends to be capital intensive though to a limited extent. This is evident in the contributions of 143.9 percent by capital to productivity increases as against 140.1 percent by labour.

10. Management Efficiency: The estimate of the efficiency parameter reveals that management is highly inefficient. The estimated efficiency parameter was - 7.441. This implies that a 100 percent increase in management input was accompanied by a fall of 744 percent in output. It would appear that management plays no role in increasing the overall efficiency of the company. This is not true on very strong empirical grounds. Management see to be contributing NOTHING to productivity increases and overall efficiency of the performance of the company because of our assumption that all manpower on rolls comprises human capital. This implies non-recognition of individual labour’s skill and the role of management. We assumed that administrative and management factors which are important policy variable inputs are completely eclipsed analytically under labour when appropriation of surplus value is the only consideration. This had made it impossible to isolate the influence of management on productivity. When the assumption is relaxed, we find that management plays a very important role in the overall productive efficiency of the company.

11. Marginal Productivity of Factor Inputs: Using the approach suggested by A. Koutsoyiannis, the marginal productivity of labour (MPL) and capital (MPK) were calculated to be 0.863 and 0.794 respectively. This shows that labour is more productive than capital. It follows that if capital is kept constant, output would change by 86.3 percent if there is a 100 percent change in labour. Conversely, output would change by 79.4 percent if there is a 100 percent change in capital keeping labour constant.

12. Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution of Factors: The marginal rate of substituting labour for capital is:

$$MRTS_{L, K} = (b_1 / b_2) (K/L)$$

$$= 1.088$$

The marginal rate of substituting capital for labour in production is calculated to be 0.920 (i.e. $MRTS_{K, L} = 0.920$). It is very clear from the estimates that it is easier to substitute labour for capital. This accounts in part for the increasing tendency of Guinness to be capital intensive.

13. Verification of Hypotheses: *This in essence means a test of the extent to which our hypotheses are valid in the light of our empirical findings. This test is carried out bearing in mind our assumptions. The first question is how valid are the assumption made? From our empirical analysis, assumptions 1, 2, 4, 6 and 7 are all valid. But the third assumption which has something to do with the homogeneity of labour of manpower on rolls seems refuted in the light of the underestimation of the role of management in production. Similarly the fifth assumption which states that the production function is homogenous of degree one seems untrue. This is because our analysis revealed that the company experiences increasing returns to scale. In spite of these limitations, we believed and very strongly too, that on the whole the assumptions are valid theoretically and empirically.*

We know that the economic performance of the company in terms of productivity (and perhaps price) is a function of the resource inputs combination and efficiency. This is proved to be true by the various estimates of factor coefficients, marginal productivities and contributions to increases in productivity. Similarly our empirical results on factor contribution to increases in productivity proved right our hypothesis that capacity utilization is a function of the technical efficiency of factor inputs. Because of the fact that capital seems to be contributing more to productivity than labour, increases in capital investment made by the company and thus becoming increasingly capital intensive seemed logical.

14. Relationship between Marginal productivity of Labour and Wages: *We hypothesized earlier that labour's productivity is a positive function of its wages. By this we mean that the higher the wage-rate, the higher labour's productivity will be. An empirical test of this hypothesis is constrained by lack of data on the trend of wage rate in Guinness over the period covered by this study. But on a priori grounds it is found that the higher the financial rewards, the more enthusiastic the Nigerian worker is to work. This means that the wage-rate influences the average Nigerian worker productivity. The case of Guinness cannot therefore be an exception. A study of productivity and labour compensation in selected industries 1964-1972 of which the beer industry was one carried out by Osakwe, revealed that the average wage-rate is a major determinant of labour's productivity. The study had revealed that the brewery industry experienced higher labour productivity because of its relatively high wage-rates vis-vis other manufacturing units. This one again disproves the popular notion of the backward bending individual supply function of labour. This goes to validate our hypothesis.*

Our assumption that labour employment is negative function of wage-rate and a positive function of labour's marginal productivity could not be tested empirically because of lack of information on the employment policy of the company. But we believed that the high minimum wage-rate in Nigeria could encourage substitution of capital for labour. Similarly the operations of the company are very highly specialized. It involves time and money to train and retrain workers. If we aggregate these and assume that they come under wages, then we will be justified to say that the employment of labour will be a negative function of wages. All these reinforce the company's choice of capital-intensive production technique.

Our analysis refutes our 6th assumption because the technique of production adopted is not solely a negative function of factor prices but solely determined by engineering and other technological factors. For example, the transformation process determines whether the production will be highly capital or labour intensive. The only allowance it makes for the adjustment of resources even at the margin is the economic decision made by management.

By and large, it is evident from our empirical analysis that our hypotheses hold. Our results are displayed systematically thus:-

$$\log Q = -7.441 + 0.745 \log L + 9.787 \log K.$$

$$(Se) = (2.451) (0.438) (0.378)$$

$$\log Q = -7.441 + 0.745 \log L + 9.787 \log K$$

$$t\text{-ratio} = (-3.6369 \quad 0.7036 \quad 2.0824)$$

$$R^2 = 0.963$$

$$R^2 = 0.945$$

$$F\text{-ratio} = 52.307$$

The sum of labour and capital coefficients equals 1.53. The result of the F-test revealed that this sum is significantly different from unity. There is therefore a clear and strong evidence of increasing returns to scale in Guinness (Nig.) Ltd., Benin City.

15. Conclusion: *This study does not pretend to provide conclusive evidence about economies of scale, marginal productivity of labour and capital and the level of productivity in Guinness (Nigeria) Ltd., and perhaps the beer industry in Nigeria. A more detailed study is called for to estimate the economic health of the beer industry in Nigeria.*

A more detailed study involving a time series and a cross-sectional analysis of data for the company and the entire beer industry would be desirable to achieve more effective results of the technical relationship between factor inputs and output. However, such a study would call for a detailed data for the company. But since some of the basic data used were not recorded in any useful form, the task of carrying out another survey to obtain the necessary information would be enormous and costly. This should not in any way deter a further empirical verification of some of the known theoretical postulated in the present literature on the theory of production. Nonetheless, the following conclusions emerged from the limited scope of the present study.

Cobb-Douglas production function formed the basis of the production analysis of Guinness (Nigeria) Limited, Benin City. The coefficient of multiple determination and F-ratio tests conducted on the data from the company revealed that the function provided a reasonably good fit to the data. Our choice of the Cobb-Douglas function is therefore vindicated. From our estimates of the labour and capital coefficients, we found that the company experiences an increasing returns to scale. Our estimate of the constant term (or efficiency parameter) gave us a negative figure. By implication it would appear that the degree of specialization and management efficiency were not reflected in the level of output. Most significantly is the implication that an increase in management input means a 744 reductions (or fall) in output. We however found out that these findings were due to our inability to obtain data for management input and hence our assumption of homogeneity of labour.

Our results of the estimates of the share of labour and capital in productivity increases revealed that capital played a more important role than labour. Another concept developed in the study was that of marginal productivity of labour and capital. With the aid of the estimated coefficients of labour and capital with the aid of the estimated coefficients of labour and capital from the Cobb-Douglas production function fitted into the data, it was possible to estimate the marginal productivity of labour and capital. We were constrained from comparing the marginal productivity of labour with the money-wage rate per person engaged in production because of lack of data. This made it impossible for us to hazard an opinion on labour compensation relative to its productivity. Whether labour was under-compensated relative to its productivity, we have no means of knowing. We also found out that our parameter estimates (i.e. the estimates of the elasticities of a change in output with respect to a percentage change in either labour or capital) were not significantly different from zero at both 5 and 10 percent level of significance using a two-tailed test. The results showed that they were only significant at 20 percent level of significance. We however, discovered from a rigorous empirical verification that this was due to our units of measurement for the labour values of total wage-bills. Similarly instead of capital service, we used the monetary value of capital. We also aggregated output instead of using the value-added approach. In effect, we expressed output, labour and capital in monetary units. This capital service and the actual costs of raw materials for the period enable us to calculate the value-added to production. Our data on raw materials were tentative ones and not to be relied upon for any meaningful statistical work.

Our findings have proved our hypotheses to be generally correct except in some few cases where we needed more information to accept or refute the hypotheses. The non-availability of data to expand the scope of this study reflects on the position of resources in the Third World and the reluctance to divulge their names let alone their data on the part of the multinationals.

16. Implications: *The implications of this study are more than met the eye. Nigeria is mono product, import dependent, peripheral capitalist economy of a retarded variety. By virtue of its development strategy it has sought to attract foreign business. By nature of its sort of capitalism the ruling classes comprise a substantial percentage of the comprador bourgeoisie. In the light of the Indigenisation Decrees of 1972 and 1977 at least 60% of all businesses must be in Nigerian hands. Guinness consequently (by definition) is a Nigerian company. The management was trained by Unilever, thinks like Unilever, but is not Unilever (in a way). The fact that the threads of control still lie in Unilever's hands is not disputed. It is closer to what Frantz Fanon would have called "black skin, white masks". The finding of Sadri (1985) had showed that the degree of specialization and management efficiency is not reflected in the level of output of Unilever owned companies in Nigeria. More significantly, he had argued, an increase in management input leads to a fall in output.*

This finding in the light of the peripheral character of Nigeria's capitalism points to what people like Sweezy, Baran, Mandel and Galtung have theorized i.e. multinationals in the Third World extract more than they contribute, if they contribute at all. In this micro study every input of the management has an adverse effect on output meaning thereby that Guinness is operating at an optimum level of exploitation. Any further exploitation will lead to diminishing returns. In other words the multinational cannot exploit the economy of the nation any further without an apparent adverse effect.

This exploitation is optimised at a point in time when the economy was beginning its downward plunge with the ushering in of the oil slump. In such a case one cannot but agree with Osvaldo Sunkel, Celso Furtado, Andre Gunder Frank and Theotonio Dos Santos and other ECLA economists in that the structure of "dependence" is such that the development of dependent capitalism reproduces the factors that prevent it from reaching an advantageous position. This is caused dialectically when an organization operates at an optimal level of exploitation, when management input must be negative and the consequent effect on output is negative. Here is case when the most profitable industry (brewing) in a dependent and retarded capitalist economy (Nigeria) cannot reach a level to enable it to compete internationally even when the degree of exploitation of the productive forces is optimal.

Less markedly, the study of Sadri 1985 points to the fact that a neo-colonial economy would have a local or national management, which is by nature more imperialist than the foreign management. This is not a contradiction but a peculiar phenomenon of retarded peripheral capitalism itself. ECLA theorists under the leadership of Raul Prebisch have expatiated at length on this phenomenon. So too the famous Prebisch-Singer thesis had postulated that the terms of trade between primary products and manufactured goods deteriorate in time. Hans Singer and Raul Prebisch had stated (in separate studies) that countries that export commodities (developing world) in time would import fewer manufactured goods relative to the given level of exports. They, in a way, explained that that it is the very structure of the market that is responsible for the inequality in the capitalist world economy and paved the way for import substitution industrializing policies of the 1970s. Nigerian thinkers readily bought that idea once the petroleum economy began to falter in the 1980s. And it is then that the conspicuous consumption of beer.

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